

Triazole based 8-formyl coumarin-glycine conjugate: A specific turn-on fluorescent probe for Cu^{II} ion[†]

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We have synthesized a new triazole based 8-formyl coumarin-glycine conjugate, (**1**), which displays turn-on fluorescent signal in presence of Cu²⁺ ion. The resulting complex displayed high selectivity towards Cu²⁺ ion not only via fluorescence emission but also exhibited a drastic color change from colorless to light green, which signifies the naked eye detection of Cu²⁺ ion. Other metal ions, e.g. Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Hg²⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Pb²⁺ and Zn²⁺ produced no obvious changes in colorimetric experiment as well as in the fluorescence emission spectra. The binding constant ($2.88 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) and ligand-metal binding ratio (1:1) were determined from fluorescence spectral data and Job's plot analysis respectively. The detection limit for the present probe towards Cu^{II} ion was calculated as low as 78 nM. Furthermore, on the basis of the ¹H NMR titration, HRMS and DFT study, probable binding mode of **1** with Cu²⁺ has been proposed.

Keywords: Glycine, coumarin, chemosensor, turn-on fluorescence, Cu^{II} ion.

Introduction

The development of optical sensing approaches for the recognition of environmentally and biologically active species, such as heavy metal ions, has been an important goal in the field of chemical sensors for several decades. Among various types of optical sensors (luminescence, absorption, reflection, etc.), a fluorescence-based one is a very attractive feature for practical applications. Its high sensitivity, instant response, non destructive character, straight forward relevance to fiber optical-based detection, and via microscopic imaging it has been capable of affording high spatial resolution. Therefore, fluorescent probes are found widespread use not only in biological studies but also in environmental monitoring¹.

After iron and zinc, copper is the third-most abundant transition metal in the human body. Copper ion plays an important role in biological systems due to its redox active na-

ture, it has an active role as a co factor in variety of enzymes^{2,3}. Thus, copper ions are essential for our health in daily basis. However, excess amount of copper may exhibits toxicity and causes neurodegenerative disease^{4,5}. Moreover, copper can also act as a significant environmental pollutant because of its extensive use in industry and agriculture^{6,7}. The maximum permissible level of Cu²⁺ in drinking water has been determined to be 20 μM by US Environmental Protection Agency (UPA)⁸. Therefore, it is essential to provide an appropriate method for recognition and determination of Cu²⁺ in water. For these reasons, many efforts have been devoted to design various fluorescent probes specific for Cu²⁺ detection. Unfortunately most of them are fluorescence turn-off system which is of course disadvantageous over turn-on probe⁹⁻¹³.

Moreover, a number of fluorescence sensors based on triazole derivatives bearing fluorescence behavior have been

[†]Invited Lecture.

reported for the determination of copper ion^{14–19}. On the other hand, coumarin based fluorescent probe for detection of Cu^{II} ion relatively rare. Coumarin was selected as the fundamental platform, because it is recognized to be a fluorescent compound, as the fluorophore arises from the fact that it possesses desirable photophysical properties such as a large Stokes shift and visible excitation and emission wavelengths^{20–22} and it is relatively easy to synthesize a large variety of structural variants^{23–25}. Coumarin-based probes are widely used in various biological assays^{26–28}.

Therefore, we have combined a water soluble amino acid, glycine ester with a fluorophore unit, coumarin, via a 1,2,3-triazole motif. Compound **1** was deliberately designed with an intervening triazole moiety between the coumarin fluorophore and the glycine unit as triazole is a potential binding unit for many ions specially for Cu^{II} ion^{29–32}. Glycine has been chosen because of its small size and high water solubility. Herein, we report for the 1st time a new colorimetric and fluorescent turn-on probe having coumarin moiety conjugated with a water soluble glycine unit for the selective and sensitive detection of Cu²⁺ ion.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

The hexamethylene tetramine, 7-hydroxy coumarin, and glycine-ethyl-ester hydrochloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used directly without further purification. CuSO₄·5H₂O, *t*-BuOH, glacial acetic acid, sodium ascorbate, propargyl bromide and K₂CO₃ were purchased from local chemical firms. The chloro acetylchloride was purchased from Alfa Aesar, *N,N*-dimethylformamide and acetonitrile (HPLC) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific and freshly distilled prior to use. Chromatography was carried out using 60–120 mesh silica gel in a column of 2.5 cm diameter. All of the necessary solvents were dried by conventional methods and distilled under an N₂ atmosphere before use. The UV-Vis absorption spectra and the fluorescence spectra were carried out in EtOH/H₂O (2/8) solutions, as stated in the corresponding Figure captions.

Instrumentation:

A BRUKER Ultra shield 400 and 100 MHz FT-NMR spec-

trometer was used for measuring ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra respectively where SiMe₄ was used as an internal standard and the chemical shifts are reported in ppm. SHIMADZU TCC-240A UV-Vis spectrophotometer was used for the study of absorption spectra at room temperature. SHIMADZU RF-5301PC spectrophotometer was used to record the fluorescence spectra. A Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrometer was employed for recording IR spectra. HRMS measurements were recorded on a XEVO-G2TOF-mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of 1:

To a well stirred solution of 8-formyl coumarin (0.100 g, 0.438 mmol) and 2-(2-azidoacetamido) acetate (0.077 g, 0.416 mmol) in 10 ml *t*-BuOH were taken in a round bottom flask equipped with a stirrer bar and added an aqueous solution of CuSO₄·5H₂O (0.087 mmol). A freshly prepared sodium ascorbate solution (0.175 mmol) was added to the mixture, and the resulting solution was stirred at room temperature for overnight. The reaction mixture was added by 30 ml of ethyl acetate, and the organic extracts were washed several times with excess of water and finally with the brine (15 ml), and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed under vacuum, and the crude product was purified by silica gel column chromatography. Elution with EtOAc/methanol (9.4:0.6, v/v) yielded compound **1** (0.136 g, 80%).

1. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 400 MHz) δ: 10.36 (s, 1H, *H*_{aldehyde}), 8.87 (s, 1H, NH), 8.26 (s, 1H, *H*_{triazole}), 8.02–7.93 (m, 2H, *H*_{coumarin}), 7.44 (d, 1H, *H*_{coumarin}), 6.36 (d, 1H, *H*_{coumarin}), 5.42 (s, 2H, OCH₂), 5.21 (s, 2H, OCH₂), 4.07 (q, 2H, NCH₂), 3.88 (d, 2H, NCH₂), 1.15 (t, 3H, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 100 MHz) δ: 187.9, 170.0, 166.7, 162.8, 160.3, 154.3, 144.9, 142.3, 135.7, 126.8, 113.7, 113.4, 112.9, 110.9, 63.2, 61.4, 52.0, 41.4, 14.4; HRMS data, *m/z* (relative intensity): 437 (M⁺+23).

Computational details:

The theoretical calculations are performed using Gaussian 09 software at the DFT level³³ with the B3LYP hybrid functional³⁴ for the geometry optimization of **1** and [1-Cu]²⁺ without any symmetry constraints in water medium employing an all-electron def2-SVPD³⁵ basis set. The real harmonic vibrational wave numbers are obtained, hence

Scheme 1. Synthesis of ligand **1**.

confirming the optimized structures. The isovalue for the visualization of molecular orbitals is set at 0.04.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of receptor **1**:

We have synthesized the receptor **1** via [2+3] cycloaddition reaction by combining 8-formyl coumarin and 2-(2-azidoacetamido) acetate in 80% yield as shown in Scheme 1. We have used glycine due to its amphoteric nature and easily water soluble properties. The final compound was characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, and HRMS study. The cation recognition properties of the receptor **1** have been examined by UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy and ¹H NMR titration along with the DFT calculations.

Visual detection of Cu²⁺:

The colorimetric sensing abilities were investigated by adding various cations (Fe³⁺, Hg²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺) to an aqueous solution of (EtOH/H₂O, 2/8, v/v) of receptor **1**. When 1 equiv of Cu²⁺ was added to the solution of **1**, an intense color changes from colorless to light green has been observed, which indicated the sensitive and selective naked eye detecting ability of receptor **1** for Cu²⁺ ion (Fig. 1). Furthermore, to examine the analytical applicability of probe **1**, we have investigated the reversibility

Fig. 1. Visual color changes observed for **1** (10^{-3} M) in ethanol/water (2/8) after addition of 1 equiv of several metal cations.

of **1** with EDTA (Fig. S4) and its action in solid support by using glass slide coated with silica.

UV-Visible absorption study:

Investigations on the photophysical properties revealed that probe, **1**, showed high selectivity to Cu²⁺ in EtOH/H₂O (2/8) solution. Sensor **1** exhibited strong absorption in ultra-violet region in the absorption at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 310$ nm and 330 nm in aqueous ethanolic solution which in accordance with the coumarin derivatives³⁶. The high energy absorption band can be attributed to a π - π^* electronic transition³⁷. Addition of low concentration of Cu²⁺ ion led to significant changes in the absorption spectra (Fig. 2). However, none of the other metal ions (Hg²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ (1 equiv)) showed any significant changes in their absorption spectra (Fig. S5). To calculate the analyte amount used in the absorption spectra, we have performed the UV-Vis absorption titration experiment. On addition of increase amount of Cu²⁺ to the probe **1**, the absorbance of 310 nm ($1114 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 330 nm ($1040 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) peaks are dramatically decreases and the peak at around 250 nm is significantly increases. A well defined isosbestic point was found at around $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 277$ nm ($1070 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), which signify the metal ligand coordination of the complex.

Fig. 2. Changes in the absorption spectra of **1** in ethanol/water (10^{-4} M) upon addition of increasing amounts of Cu²⁺ ion up to 1 equiv.

Fluorescence study:

To further assess the selectivity and sensitivity of chemosensor **1** towards various metal ions, the fluorescence emission spectra of **1** have been recorded in the presence of

several metal ions in EtOH/H₂O solution (Fig. S6). However, Cu²⁺ was the only metal ion that caused significant fluorescence enhancement (Fig. 3). To further evaluate the binding ratio between metal ion and receptor **1**, we have performed the fluorescence titration of Cu²⁺ ion. During Cu²⁺ titration with **1**, the free ligand shows weaker intensity band at around 384 nm when it excited at around 310 nm (Fig. 3). After the successive addition of increasing concentration of Cu²⁺ ion to the receptor **1**, the emission intensity gradually reached at maximum and it saturated after 1 equiv of Cu²⁺ ion. These

Fig. 3. Changes in the fluorescence of **1** (10^{-6} M) in EtOH/H₂O, upon the gradual addition up to 1 equiv of Cu^{II} ion, with excitation at 310 nm.

observations indicated that Cu²⁺ is the only metal ion that readily binds with receptor **1**, causing significant fluorescence turn-on and permitting highly selective detection of Cu²⁺. The significance change in fluorescence intensity for **1** in presence of Cu^{II} ion as well as in presence of other competitive cations have been represented as bar diagram in Fig. 4. To investigate the binding assays using the method of continuous variations (Job's plot) suggest a 1:1 binding model with Cu²⁺ for **1**. The maximum emission change was observed when the molar ratio of **1** to Cu²⁺ was 0.5, indicating a 1:1 stoichiometry for the complex (Fig. S7). This result has also been confirmed by HRMS data, where a peak at *m/z* 477 corresponding to the 1:1 complex of **1** with Cu²⁺ (Fig. S8).

Fig. 4. Bar diagram representation of fluorescence spectra emission at 384 nm of the sensor **1** (2.0×10^{-6} M) in EtOH/H₂O (2:8, v/v) solutions in the presence of Cu²⁺ (1 equiv) and the cations Fe³⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Hg²⁺ (1 equiv).

The binding constant value of Cu²⁺ with probe **1** has been determined from the fluorescence intensity data according to the modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation^{38,39} by using the linear regression, $\log [(F - F_0)/(F_m - F)] = \log K + n \log [M]$, where *F*, *F_m*, and *F₀* are the emission intensities of **1** as an intermediate of Cu²⁺ concentration, in the absence of Cu²⁺ ion and at a concentration of complete interaction respectively. *K* is the binding constant, and [*M*] is the Cu²⁺ concentration. From the plot the value of '*K*' extracted as the binding constant value 2.88×10^4 M⁻¹ for **1** with Cu²⁺ (Fig. S9).

Further, in order to elucidate the sensitivity of receptor **1**, we have carried out fluorescence titration of **1** (7.8×10^{-6} M) with Cu²⁺ ion (7.8×10^{-6} M) in EtOH/H₂O (2/8; v/v). There is no detectable shift was observed for the probe **1** up to the 0.05 equiv. of analyte concentration. An appreciable enhancement in the signal intensity was observed in the presence of 0.1 equiv of Cu²⁺. These experiments show detectable limit (DL) with **1** is 7.8×10^{-8} M (78 nM) for Cu²⁺.

In order to evaluate the practical importance of **1** as a Cu²⁺ selective fluorescence probe, competition experiments were carried out. A solution of **1** (10^{-6} M) was treated separately with 1 equiv of Cu²⁺ in presence of 1 equiv each of interference metal ions (Pb²⁺, Hg²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mg²⁺). Very little or no obvious interference with the detection of Cu²⁺ could be observed (Fig. S10). These results evidently demonstrate the high selectivity for Cu²⁺ over other metal ions. Thus, **1** can be utilized for the detection of Cu²⁺ ion in the

presence of other competing ions.

We have taken the glass slide and immersing those glass slides into an ethanolic solution of **1** (0.1 M) for investigating its action in solid support. The glass slide containing receptor **1** was utilized to sense different cations. As shown in Fig. 5, when different cation solutions were added to the test kits, an obvious color change was observed only with Cu²⁺ solu-

Fig. 5. Color changes of silica gel soaked with **1** upon addition into aqueous solution of Cu²⁺ ion.

tion. Therefore, the test strips can conveniently detect Cu²⁺ in solid state medium as well.

¹H NMR titration study:

¹H NMR titration was carried out to understand the coordination mode and the possible binding interaction site of **1** with Cu²⁺ metal ion in DMSO-*d*₆. As shown in Fig. 6 upon addition of 1 equiv of Cu²⁺ ion to the receptor **1**, the H_a proton of triazole moiety got downfield shifted from 8.23 ppm to 8.35 ppm and the H_b proton got downfield shifted from 4.30 to 4.50 ppm indicating that the O atom of the carbonyl carbon of ester moiety and the N atom of the triazole unit might be coordinated to Cu²⁺ ion. Meanwhile the H_c proton has also been slightly shifted from 4.13 to 4.18 ppm. After 1 equiv the peaks were not changed upon further addition of Cu²⁺ ion. On the basis of the ¹H NMR titration measurements, HRMS data and Job's plot analysis, we propose that the Cu^{II}

Fig. 6. Proposed mode of binding between receptor **1** and Cu²⁺ ion in DMSO-*d*₆.

binding (1:1) mechanism of receptor **1** involves the O atom and the N atom of carbonyl carbon of ester group and triazole unit respectively.

Computational details:

The optimized structure of the ligand (**1**) and complex $[1\text{-Cu}]^{2+}$ in bidentate configuration calculated at B3LYP/def2-SVPD/CPCM level are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. The selected bond lengths are as follows: Cu-O: 1.9430 Å and Cu-N: 1.9346 Å. As shown in Fig. 9 the spin resolved frontier molecular orbitals for both the spins feature Cu d-type orbital as

Fig. 7. DFT optimized structures of **1** calculated at B3LYP/def2-SVPD/CPCM level. Color code: H: white, C: gray, O: red, N: blue.

Fig. 8. DFT optimized structures of $[1\text{-Cu}]^{2+}$ calculated at B3LYP/def2-SVPD/CPCM level. Color code: H: white, C: gray, O: red, N: blue, Cu: orange pink.

HOMO while 2-centered and 3-centered π -type orbitals for alpha-spin and beta-spin respectively centered on 8-formyl coumarin feature as LUMO. Similar to LUMOs of $[1\text{-Cu}]^{2+}$, in the case of (**1**) 3-centered and 2-centered π -type orbitals positioned on 8-formyl coumarin feature HOMO and LUMO respectively.

Fig. 9. The frontier molecular orbitals (spin-resolved) of optimized **1** and $[1\text{-Cu}]^{2+}$ calculated at B3LYP/def2-SVPD/CPCM level. Isovalue: 0.04.

Conclusions

In this present work, a novel colorimetric and fluorescence turn-on chemosensor has been designed and synthesized. The metal-ligand binding ratio as well as the plausible binding site of the receptor has also been suggested on the basis of UV-Vis absorption, fluorescence emission and ¹H NMR titration study along with the DFT calculations. The receptor **1** specifically detects Cu²⁺ ion with very low limit of detection (78 nM). To the best of our knowledge, the receptor **1** is the 1st example of triazole appended coumarin-amino acid (glycine) conjugate which exhibits turn-on fluorescence emission for Cu²⁺ ion in aqueous environment.

Supporting information data

¹H, ¹³C, and HRMS data of **1**, UV-Vis absorption spectra upon titration with different metal ions, fluorescence spectra upon titration with different metal ions, HRMS spectrum of [**1**Cu]²⁺ and Job's plot.

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